

Semiotic Analysis of The Tik Tok Application in Android Phone

Gita Amelia

Student of Master of English Education, University of Lampung, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Tik Tok has become a popular way for people to express themselves in recent years. Semiotic analysis of the tik tok application in android phone is the title of this research. The purpose of this research is to describe the semiotics analysis of tik tok application through connotative and denotative meanings. The qualitative descriptive method is used by the authors in this study. Observation is the way for gathering data. Choosing the symbol to be studied is the first step. The findings show that twenty-five different symbols in the Tik Tok application on android phone have meaning. Based on the symbols, each of them attend a different function. The conclusions is by using this application users can share videos, interact with others, explore the globe and learn English.

KEYWORDS: Android, Linguistic, Semiotic, Symbol, Tik Tok.

INTRODUCTION

Humans need language to convey a message, purpose or meaning. (Stockwell, 2013) language is a system of symbols that are meaningful and articulate sound (produced by a tool) that is arbitrary and conventional. Using social media is one of the ways to communicate and communicate with people all over the world. Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, Twitter, Tik Tok and other social media are the tools that people need now. Tiktok is a new social network that many people use to share videos.

Tik Tok is a video sharing software that allows users to record videos and apply digital effects to photos before sharing them with their followers. In addition to making the features of Tik Tok work, they must use persuasive statements, phrases or jargons, in other words, try to get the audience to use the app. The logo must be attractive, memorable and easy to understand for all users. On the other hand, people need to understand the meaning of the logo. For example, shards of glass in a box indicate that it is easy to destroy. Based on the symbol or sign itself, anyone can determine its meaning.

Semiotics is a branch of psychology that explains how signs work. Icons, symbols, and indexes are three types of signs that can be found. The theory of semiotics is crucial to the systematic study of the production and interpretation of signs, how they work and how they contribute to human life, therefore it is necessary to analyze this study. Humans are creatures of signs and their lives are full of signs because human signs can communicate with each other through intermediaries. Therefore, the researcher is interested in studying the semiotics of the Tik Tok logo under the title "*Semiotic analysis of the Tik Tok Application on Android Phone*". In addition, the purpose of this work is to analyze the descriptions and functions of Tik Tok application symbols through connotative and denotative in Android phone using semiotic analysis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Linguistics

Linguistics is the scientific study of human language. As such, it examines the ways in which members of a given discourse communities conceptualize their experience, encode it into linguistic form, and then use that code in social interaction. Linguistics considers human language as a universal and recognized part of human behavior and human abilities. Linguistics is defined as the science of language or linguistics. King T. Nasr (1984), linguistics considers human language a universal and recognizable part of human behavior and human abilities. Linguists study language patterns and the principles that support them after learning one or more languages other than their mother tongue and find themselves drawn to the languages themselves or to the challenges of learning new languages. Linguistics students are often drawn to the excitement of learning and participating in a field that is still in its infancy, yet rapidly developing, regardless of their initial motivation. Linguistics students not only study problems related to language, but also receive a broad education that crosses traditional disciplinary boundaries.

Linguistics is the scientific study of language (Kridalaksana, 2009:144). Tarigan (1986) defines linguistics as the body of knowledge obtained by applying the scientific method to the study of linguistic phenomena. Learning linguistics is crucial because

language is the primary means of communication for all people. People use different languages to fulfill their needs in their daily life. The ability to communicate with other people is a basic human need, because people are social creatures by nature who communicate with each other. Linguistics is a discipline that studies language in its broadest sense. Broadly speaking, this means that all features and components of the language are covered. This shows that the goal is not limited to one language (for example only Indonesian), but all the languages of the world.

Applied Linguistic

Applied linguistics is a branch of linguistics that deals with the application of concepts in everyday life, for example in language teaching. Applied linguistics is a branch of linguistics that applies linguistic theory to solving real problems, most often in the field of language teaching. According to experts Richards and Schmidt (2002: 320), applied linguistics is defined as the study of learning and teaching a second and foreign language. Schmit and Celce-Muria di Davies (2004: 4) define applied linguistics as the application or use of what we know about language, how it is learned, and how it is used to achieve a goal or solve a problem in the real world. In Davies de Grabe (2004: 5), applied linguistics seeks to solve language problems that people encounter in the real world, whether they are students, teachers, administrators, researchers, lawyers and service providers, social workers, decision makers, lexicographers, translators or other types of business clients. For example, linguists can use what they know about how children and adults learn languages to design teaching materials and modules for teaching a second language and effectively monitor student progress. Teachers can use what they know about how people use language in everyday life to ensure that their teaching prepares students for the kinds of interactions they are most likely to encounter. Semiotics is the field of applied linguistics that is the focus of this study.

Semiotic

Semiotics comes from the Greek word "*Semion*" which etymologically means "*sign*". Therefore, the sign is characterized as a social contract already embodied in the past that recognizes some meaning. (Sobur, 2009, p. 95) A sign can be identity, culture, language or something else, and it also requires a social norm to agree on the interpretation of its signs. For example, in Indonesia, especially in Java, when a person dies, there is a yellow flag around the deceased's home, but in Sumatera, the color of the flag is different and the yellow flag represents a celebration, such as a wedding or something, such an event. Semiotics is the study of myths and metaphors and the science of the meaning of signs. Symbols, codes, meanings, myths and metaphors are the basic concepts of semiotics. Denotation is a process that combines the vulgarity and meaning of a sign. The labeling process is divided into two stages: first-order and second-order labeling. The relationship between the signifier and the signified is described in the first order of meaning. Barthes calls the first order of signification, and it refers to the apparent meaning of the sign. Since Barthes is a follower of Saussure, their concepts of signifier and signified letter are similar. For example, the white and red uniform is a symbol of the elementary student uniform. According to Saussure, signs are divided into three categories: a) Material aspects of signs (sounds, letters, images, movement and shapes) b. Signifier refers to specific aspects of language, such as what is said or heard and written or read. c. Mental images, thoughts and concepts are represented. The mental parts of language are known as signs. These three elements must be perfect, and without any of them, no sign can be considered even improbable. Therefore, the signified is the idea or what the signifier conveys, and the relationship between the signified and the signifier is called a meaning-producing symbolic relationship. For example, the word "*Supermarket*" can be a label because it has a label (the word itself) and a sign (an actual place where we can shop).

Symbol

A symbol is a representation of an object signified by law, usually a combination of general ideas that cause the symbol to be taken to refer to that object. A symbol, on the other hand, is a sign that has no physical resemblance to the meaning it conveys. Symbolic signs, like most words in any language, are arbitrarily related to what they represent. They are essentially signs that have an arbitrary relationship to those objects, such as language in general (as well as individual languages, alphabets, punctuation marks, words, phrases and sentences), numbers and other codes. Objects, events, speech sounds and written forms given human meaning are called symbols. The most important tool for symbolizing people is language. Signs and symbols are used in painting, dance, music, architecture, expression, face, gesture, posture, jewelry, clothing, ceremonies, religion, kinship, nationality, etiquette, space, possession of goods, and many other modes of communication. A person can give meaning to any event, action or object that is associated with thoughts, ideas and feelings. Considerable research in anthropology and other disciplines focuses on understanding

the use of symbols as one important characteristic of people (Saiffudin, 205: 290). People no longer exist only in the physical universe, but also in the symbolic universe. Language, myth, art and religion are all part of this cosmos, and the intertwined threads form a metaphorical woven web, like disparate objects. Symbols or signs are concepts that people consider as a unique property of something else, either through logical-analytical properties or associations of thought or fact. A symbol stimulates or conveys a message that causes a person to think or act. Charles Peirce, the founder of modern semiotics, identified three types of signs: (1) an iconic sign that reflects its object in a certain way; (2) index marks physically associated with the item; and (3) symbols, such as language, which are meaningful to an object because they are interpreted as such through convention and use (Saiffudin, 2005:291).

TikTok

Tik Tok is a popular and in-demand application worldwide. Tik Tok allows users to make 15-60 second videos with music, filters and other creative elements. This program was developed by a Chinese company. Indonesia is a country in Southeast Asia. This app was named the best app of 2018 in the Google Play Store. This program is enjoyed by teenagers, young children and even adults who need entertainment. Tik Tok has its own personality. Tik Tok videos contain a "watermark" in the form of a username that identifies them from videos posted by other apps. Since this program is used by many people of all ages, it is possible that some of the content may contain harmful elements. The Tik Tok app is an Indonesian social media platform that is rapidly growing into mainstream culture in 2020. In fact, Tik Tok is not a new social media in Indonesia, because Tik Tok has become a new trend and popular culture in Indonesia in recent years, especially in 2018 and 2019. Popular culture is a culture that is appreciated by many people and is not related to a certain social class. In the current digital age, because the ease of access to information has a huge impact on popular culture in a country, popular culture has more influence (Sorrels, 2015). Because millennial are very active and intensive with new technologies that are widely used by millennial in Indonesia, the millennial generation played an important role in the development of today's popular culture in Indonesia.

For many reasons, including (Yang, Zhao and Ma, 2019) short videos that are close to reality and common conditions, Tik Tok can become a popular culture in Indonesia. First, Tik Tok is close to the reality of society, and the main theme is intertwined with entertainment, science and fashion, which easily attract the attention of the audience, a simple example of Tik Tok short videos, content creators can create short forms. Videos content (from 15 seconds to 3 minutes). Second, users' rights to privacy According to the communication theory, the application Tik Tok gives freedom to its users, that is, the purpose of the existence of video is to help people express themselves and capture a good life (Mancini and Hallin, 2012). The third is great content that focuses on current events. Tik Tok users, who are mostly millennials, are very interested in current trends, which include fitness, emotional interpretations, amazing landscapes, beauty and physical gestures that symbolize current fashion trends. Then, Indonesian celebrity influencers follow in the footsteps of celebrities using Tik Tok. While only a few celebrities used Tik Tok in the country in 2017, many celebrities are creating their own Tik Tok profiles and posting them on their other social media accounts. Finally, Tik Tok advertises its applications in an attractive way and at low costs, and adds enjoyable content, which can lead to rapid dissemination of video (George and Bennet, 2005).

METHODS

This study used Sudaryanto (1993) qualitative descriptive data, which verbally described human activities and focused on a representative sample as the most significant data. It was an excellent choice for this study because it describes the characteristics of Tik Tok. As a result, the qualitative description matches the description and focuses more on the data presented. This study was descriptive because the author was the main vehicle that described the data and analyzed the results for solving the research problem. Tik Tok was chosen as the topic of the research because it has many attractive components to explore, as shown by its logo. In this study, the following steps were taken to collect the data: record the data about the official logo of Tik Tok, get images from the data to analyze the data as a population, classify the data and analyze the data using semiotic theory to determine connotations and signs meaning is contained in Tik Tok.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

• Data 1

This symbol works to show videos that have been recommended by tik-tok itself or videos that come from our followers and people we follow. This symbol is in the form of a house with a door in the middle and the color is white.

• Data 2

This symbol serves as an option for us as viewers to like the video that we see or not and if we choose to like it then the video will be stored in a special place for the collection of videos that we like. This symbol is in the shape of a heart and the color is white if we don't click it but if we click on it will be red.

• Data 3

This symbol serves as a video sharing if we want to share the video that we see on tik tok with other people and this is connected to the WhatsApp and Instagram applications. This symbol is in the shape of an arrow and is curved sideways in and the color is white.

• Data 4

This is a symbol that shows the filters that we or other people use in tik tok videos. This symbol can take various forms depending on the tik tok filter that we use.

•Data 5

This symbol functions as a report for users, if users feel that the videos on Tik Tok that we see contain harmful elements, hate speech, bully, and pornography or spam, we can use this symbol. This symbol is in the form of a circle with an exclamation point in the middle.

• Data 6

This symbol works if the user wants to get money from tik tok the user can click this and then invite friends to join tik tok and tik tok will transfer some money to the user and the user can withdraw the money. This symbol is in the form of a green place with a collection of coins in it.

• Data 7

This symbol functions as a notification bell if the user wants to know that the person they are following will be live on tik-tok. This symbol is in the shape of a bell.

•Data 8

This symbol works if we want to know the audio that is playing or the song that is playing in the tik tok video that we watch. This symbol is in the form of a circle like a CD that is playing and when the video is played there will be many symbols for the tone of the song.

•Data 9

This symbol serves to view our profile as a tik tok user to edit the name and see a collection of tik tok videos that we have ever made. This symbol is in the form of a half-body with a circular head and a semicircular body.

•Data 10

This symbol is used to search for the video we want to find in the tik tok search or find video recommendations from tik tok for us. This symbol is shaped like a magnifying glass with a round head.

•Data 11

This symbol works if a tik tok user wants to follow the video maker's account in tik tok or unfollow the account. This symbol is in the form of a red circle with a plus sign in it. If we click on it, the plus sign will turn into a check mark.

•Data 12

This symbol serves to see the inbox in our account that comes from users or people who follow us. This symbol is a square with a curved bottom with a minus sign in it.

•Data 13

This symbol serves as a place if we want to see someone's live. Live itself means we can interact directly with the person via virtual. This symbol is in the form of a television with a live description in it.

•Data 14

This symbol serves to convey user comments to other users in tik tok. This symbol is in the form of a white circle with a curve below it and 3 dots in it.

• Data 15

This symbol serves to add friends in tik tok. Through our contacts, invite friends and use friends on facebook. This symbol is in the form of a picture of a person whose head is in the shape of a circle with a plus sign next to it.

• Data 16

This symbol is for viewing videos, sounds, effects, comments, hashtags and products from tik tok. This symbol is in the form of a rectangle underneath it like a triangular piece.

• Data 17

This symbol contains the videos that we make but only we ourselves can see the videos and people can't access them. This symbol is in the form of a lock.

• Data 18

This symbol is the same as the previous tik tok bonus symbol, users can earn money by adding their friends to join as tik tok users. This symbol is in the form of a yellow coin with the words Rp in it.

• Data 19

This symbol serves to share the user's tik tok account through many application platforms. It can also be used as an account report, block and send message. This symbol is in the form of a line with three lines stacked together.

• Data 20

This symbol serves to view videos that have been liked by other users but this depends on the changer whether he/she activates this feature or not, if the user disables it then we cannot see the videos he/she has liked. This symbol is in the shape of a heart in the center of which is an ellipse symbol crossed by a diagonal line.

• Data 21

This symbol serves to follow the account that we want to make friends. This symbol is in the form of a red square with a description of the following sentence in it.

• Data 22

This symbol serves to view other users' Instagram accounts that are linked to Tik Tok. This symbol is in the form of a camera, Square with a circle inside.

• Data 23

This symbol serves to view followers from other user accounts. This symbol is a square with a small triangle inside that is upside down.

• Data 24

This symbol serves to upload videos or create new videos on tiktok which can vary in length, which can be 15 seconds, 1 minute and 3 minutes. This symbol is in the shape of a square with a little green and a little red in each square and inside is a plus sign.

• Data 25

This symbol serves to see incoming messages from our followers or people we follow can also be used to view messages that we send. This symbol is shaped like a plane made of paper with a line in the middle.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of this study, the authors conclude that the symbols used in Tik-Tok are compatible with these functions. Signs of meaning and significance correspond to the meaning of logos or symbols. Logos are quite useful to convey their meaning. Even without written instructions, users can use Tik Tok with little knowledge of symbols. In addition, some symbols include descriptions that make Tik Tok easier for users to understand.

The author hopes that the study of this topic will help others in the study and study of semiotic analysis. It was suggested that future scholars interested in semiotics could improve and strengthen this research. For teachers who want to explain and explore semiotics topics. It was suggested that this study could be used as a semiotic analysis teaching material for teachers and combined with the application; it could help the teacher to teach students to learn English. For readers and students interested in semiotic analysis. They can apply such a topic to learn English through the tik tok application.

REFERENCES

1. Anson, W. (1988). Determining your identity's asset value. Identity Management Conference, Dallas, TX.
2. Davies, Alan and Cathie Elder (eds) (2004), *The Handbook of Applied Linguistics*, Oxford: Blackwell.
3. Fromkin, V., Rodman, R., & Hyams, N. (2011). *An introduction to language*. Cengage Learning.
4. George, A. L., & Bennett, A. (2005). *Case studies and theory development in the social sciences*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press
5. Heilbrunn, B. (1998). *A Semiotic Analysis of Consumer Brand Relationship*. Hampstead: Prentice-Hall.
6. Kridalaksana, Harimurti. (2009). *Kamus Linguistik*. Jakarta: Gramedia.
7. Mancini, P., & Hallin, D. C. (2012). Some caveats about comparative research in media studies. In H. A. Semetko & M. Scammell (Eds.), *Sage handbook of political communication* (pp. 509-517). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
8. Nasr, Raja T. (ed.) (1984). *The Essentials of Linguistic Science*. London: Longman Richards, Jack C and Richard Schmidt, *Longman Dictionary of Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics*, 3rd Ed., London: Pearson Education Limited, 2002.
9. Saiffudin, Achmad Fedyani. (2005). *Antropologi Kontemporer: Suatu Pengantar Kritis Mengenai Paradigma*. Jakarta: Prenada Media.

10. Saussure, D. F. (1960). *Course in General Linguistics*. London: Peter Owen (rev. 1974).
11. Sobur, Alex. (2006). *Semiotika Komunikasi*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya. Bandung.
12. Sorrels. (2015). *Globalizing Intercultural Communication*. California: Sage Publications, Inc.
13. Stockwell, G. (2013). Tracking learner usage of mobile phones for language learning outside of the classroom. In P. Hubbard, M. Schulz & B. Smith (Eds), *Learner-computer interaction in language education: A festschrift in honor of Robert Fischer* (pp. 118-136). San Marcos, TX: CALICO.
14. Sudaryanto. (1993). *Method dan teknik analisis bahasa*. Yogyakarta: Duta Wacana University Press.
15. Tarigan, Henry Guntur. (1986). *Menulis: Sebagai Suatu Keterampilan Berbahasa*. Bandung: Angkasa
16. Yang, S., Zhao, Y., & Ma, Y. (2019). Analysis of the Reasons and Development of Short Video Application: Taking Tik Tok as an Example. 9th International Conference on Information and Social Science..